

Analysis of the Gross Motor Skills of Children Aged 5-6 Years in Football Games at TK Negeri Pembina Sibolangit

Aldi Pranata Barus^{1*}, Aman Simaremare²
State University of Medan

Corresponding Author: Aldi Pranata Barus aldipranatabarus01@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

This research was conducted with the aim of describing the gross motor skills of children aged 5-6 years in the aspects of: 1) Strength, 2) Agility, 3) Balance through playing football. The type of research used is descriptive qualitative. The subjects in this study were 10 children aged 5-6 years at TK Negeri Pembina Sibolangit. The results showed that: 1) the gross motor skills of children in the strength aspect showed that 70% had developed as expected and 30% had not developed as expected. 2) children's motor skills in the agility aspect show that 60% of children develop as expected and 40% have not developed as expected. 3) gross motor skills of children in the aspect of balance, 80% of children's abilities have developed as expected and 20% have not developed as expected.

INTRODUCTION

Early childhood is a child aged 0-6 years whose growth and development during this period is often said to be the golden age. At this time it is very important to develop children's character and personality through teaching so that the child's potential for personal development in terms of intelligence, interests and talents can be realized optimally.

Early childhood education (PAUD) through school education is an important basis for developing children's talents, including six aspects of child development which include: physical and motoric, cognitive, social emotional, language and arts, religious and moral values. This development requires patience and skills in optimizing the child's development. In accordance with the goals of developing gross motor skills in early childhood, preschool teachers are expected to be able to help and develop them with various appropriate efforts or strategies from the Ministry of National Education (Anggreni, 2022).

One aspect of development that needs to be stimulated from an early age is the child's physical and motoric aspects. Physical motor skills are the growth process of early childhood following the cephalocaudal principle, namely that the head and upper part of the body develop first, so that the upper part appears larger than the lower part (Fatmawati, 2020). Early childhood physical motor skills need to be stimulated from an early age, because it can influence other developments such as the child's intellectual intelligence and also influence the child's social processes. This is in accordance with a question by Hurlock (Fatmawati, 2020), who believes that physical motor development influences other developments, especially children's intellectual development, so that children can adapt to the school environment well. If a child's motor development is normal, this allows the child to be able to play and socialize with their peers, whereas for children who are stunted or abnormal, this can prevent the child from socializing with their peers.

Early childhood motor skills are divided into two, namely gross motor skills and fine motor skills. Gross motor skills are the ability to use gross muscles which are influenced by part or all of the body parts which are influenced by the child's own maturity. For example, the ability to kick, run, go up and down stairs, jump and train strength (Hurlock, 1998). This means that in the skills of children at this age: the child is able to catch something, the child is able to walk, the child is able to jump, the child is able to kick, the child is able to run, the child is able to punch and swing his arms, and the child is able to go up and down stairs. This statement is supported by Gallahue (Anggraini, 2022), stating that children's gross motor skills are closely related to the work of the large muscles of the human body.

One good strategy for developing physical aspects of children's gross motor skills is to play, because this can train children to use body control and gross movements and also use gross muscles. One game that can stimulate children's gross motor skills is soccer. The game of soccer is a game that can develop children's gross motor skills and abilities, where in its development

this game can introduce how to control the body, kick the ball, dribble the ball, and catch the ball. This is reinforced by the opinion of Primasoni (2017), that the game of soccer really helps the physical, motoric and mental growth and development of children. The game of soccer involves a lot of gross body movements and also communication between children, training and the environment will also have an impact on the abilities of young children. The game of soccer also trains children's agility and balance. The child will try to maintain his body so that the ball that is kicked towards the child can be received well. Not only receiving the ball, children will also do activities such as dribbling and throwing the ball so that children will be enthusiastic about playing these games, therefore playing ball is a game that can train children's gross motor skills well. This is confirmed by research by Rini Andriani, (2016), who suggests that gross motor skills can be stimulated through sports games, one of which is by playing with ball.

In fact, in the researchers' observations when conducting initial observations at TK Negeri Pembina Sibolangit, gross motor skills had not yet developed optimally, where there were still children who were not yet capable of strength, agility and balance when playing football, as well as not being able to catch with their feet. perfect, not yet able to run well, not yet able to kick, and not yet able to stand on one leg. This occurs due to a lack of physical activity in daily learning, a lack of media to stimulate gross motor development, media and game tools that are still lacking are inhibiting factors in children's gross motor development. In this regard, researchers are interested in analyzing the gross motor skills of children aged 5-6 years at TK Negeri Pembina Sibolangit.

Based on the background above, the researcher wants to conduct research with the title "Analysis of the Gross Motor Skills of Children Aged 5-6 Years Through the Game of Football in TK Negeri Pembina Sibolangit".

LITERATURE REVIEW

Gross Motor Ability

Gross motor development in early childhood is an action that occurs in humans and occurs only once in a human's life, at this stage of development it occurs in preschool children. At this stage gross motor development involves heavy activities and requires large movements and muscles. General gross motor development at the age of 5-6 years old can walk well, can go up and down stairs well, can run, can jump, can climb well. Motor behavior requires functional coordination between nerves and muscles as well as cognitive, behavioral and motor functions. Motor behaviors that must be mastered by pre-school children include walking and playing with friends. Gross motor development requires movement and will make bones and muscles stronger. Lots of movement will control the weight of obese children and the child will increase their enthusiasm so that the child's body will be healthy. Among other things, they are interrelated in

supporting the optimization of children's gross motor skills perfectly according to how to stimulate them.

Zukilfi (Samsudin, 2008), believes that gross motor skills are the basis of everything related to body movements. Where it is explained in motor development that the determining elements are muscles, nerves and brain. In this element, each role is carried out in a positive interaction. And according to Susanto (2012), explains that gross motor skills are movement patterns that involve most of the body and require a lot of energy because basically this activity is carried out using gross muscles and provides coordination in maintaining the stability or balance of the body in carrying out daily movements. day. The explanation also includes examples of gross motor movements such as: lying on your back, lying face down, walking and running, jumping, throwing a ball, catching a ball and kicking a ball.

Several characteristics of gross motor development according to Bredekamp and Copple (Sujiono, 2015), are as follows:

- a. Stand on your tiptoes in a straight line with your hands on your hips.
- b. Jump on both feet alternately and jump in all directions. And is able to play games that require fast reactions.
- c. Walk on the footbridge and maintain balance on the footbridge
- d. Already able to throw the ball with one hand or two hands.

The factors that influence the gross motor skills of early childhood are the child's nervous development system, because this is the most basic thing in controlling motor skills in humans, the child's physical condition, this is because the physical condition of a healthy child will affect the level of development of less developed children. both physically, and the child's motivation as well as a supportive environment in improving the child's motor skills.

Basic Movements and Basic Techniques for Early Childhood Football

The game of soccer is very suitable to be played by anyone, including young children, because it can stimulate the physical motoric aspects of children. One of the important tasks in training in early childhood soccer is the evaluation process where at the stage of providing appropriate training for children, which ones are necessary. improved in children. Primasoni (2017), stated that training young children is not an easy task, training must have a variety of techniques, trainers must not only train a combination of technique, tactics, physical, mental, but also must be able to combine communication, the child's age and mind. child. More complexly, training must also take into account the child's physical development and early childhood abilities.

Primasoni (2017), believes that in football, basic tactics and techniques are a component of playing. Basic tactics and techniques are a level of understanding regarding technical, physical, mental and character abilities which of course will influence an individual's performance.

The basics of movement in a soccer game are elements of movement that students must be able to carry out, for example: walking, jumping and rolling are physical activities and are the basis of movement in training children's physical and physical fitness, which is also often called general physical. Physical strength concerns components such as endurance and explosive power, speed, flexibility, strength and agility. In football there are basic techniques that must be carried out which cover all elements of movement. Basic playing techniques play an important role in establishing the patterns and dynamics of the game in football.

The following are the basic techniques in football.

1. Dribbling
In soccer, this technique aims to control the ball using the feet.
2. Shooting
This basic soccer technique is very useful for scoring goals and providing passes to teammates.
3. Passing
Passing the ball is one of the basic soccer techniques, usually this technique is used to penetrate the opponent's defense. In this concept, teammates are usually already in the opponent's defense.
4. Holding the ball
In the game of soccer, holding the ball is a movement used to receive passes from teammates. In the process of receiving a pass, you must maintain body coordination so that it remains balanced and can hold the ball well.

In this activity, of course there are steps that must be taken to ensure the activity runs smoothly, some of these steps are as follows:

- a. Prepare some plastic balls.
- b. Prepare a suitable field.
- c. Prepare a goal for the child to kick.
- d. Make a path for children to dribble the ball.
- e. Explain the flow of the game to children.
- f. Motivate children so that they can carry out activities with confidence.
- g. Warm up first.
- h. Give directions to children what to do.
- i. Repeat activities with children so that they are

satisfied in the gameprocess.

- j. After the game is finished, do cool down activities.
- k. When ending the game, congratulate the children and motivate them to be more enthusiastic.

METHODOLOGY

The type of research used during the research is qualitative research, which is research that studies people with the aim of understanding the context and directing it to a detailed and in-depth description of the portrait of conditions in a natural context according to the point of view being studied.

The research was conducted at TK Negeri Pembina Sibolangit, Sibolangit District, Deli Serdang Regency, North Sumatra Province. The research was carried out from April to July 2023.

In accordance with the objectives of the research to be carried out, the subjects in this research are children aged 5-6 years at TK Negeri Pembina Sibolangit with a total of 10 children.

The data collection techniques used in this research were questionnaires and observations using observation guidelines.

The analysis technique used in this research is analyzing the data proposed by Miles and Huberman (Nursafia, 2020), namely data reduction, data display, drawing conclusions.

These steps are as follows:

- a. First: Data reduction, after collecting it, it is done by sorting the data, creating themes, categorizing, focusing the data according to its field, discarding, arranging the data in one way and making a summary in units of analysis, after that, checking the data again and grouping it according to with the problem under study. After being reduced, the data that is in accordance with the research objectives will be described in sentence form so that a complete picture of the research problem is obtained.
- b. Second: data display (data presentation). This form of analysis is carried out by presenting data in narrative form, where the researcher describes the results of the data findings in the form of graphic sentence descriptions, relationships between categories that are sequential and systematic.
- c. Third: drawing conclusions. Even though in data reduction the conclusions have been drawn, they are not permanent, there is still the possibility of additions and reductions occurring. So the conclusion stage has been found in accordance with the evidence that has been obtained in the field accurately and factually. Starting with data collection, data selection, data categorization, data description and data drawing conclusions. Data obtained from observations are presented in firm language to avoid errors. Then it is

presented in sections describing the data that is deemed necessary to support the research statement.

Validity in qualitative research needs to be carried out. Lincoln and Guna (Nursafia, 2020), provide standards for the validity of qualitative research data. According to both of them, there are several standards or criteria to guarantee validity, namely credibility standards, transferability standards and dependability.

RESEARCH RESULTS

In accordance with the results of field observations that have carried out research using observation and documentation methods for approximately 2 months at TK Negeri Pembina Sibolangit. From the results of observations carried out by researchers, it was found that the gross motor skills of children aged 5-6 years at TK Negeri Pembina Sibolangit were not all evenly distributed. This can be seen from the presentation of the indicators and descriptors that have been created. The following is a description of the research findings on the grossmotor skills of children aged 5-6 years at the Sibolangit State Kindergarten:

Kicking and Passing Power

The first indicator of gross motor ability is the child's strength when the child is playing football. In this indicator there are 2 descriptors, namely kicking the ball towards the target that the researcher has prepared and passing the ball towards his playing partner. From the results of observations and data collection that have been carried out, the data obtained is that there are 3 children whose gross motor skills have not yet developed optimally. Of the 10 children who were observed, only Desman, Afifah, and Putera had not developed as expected. This data can be seen from the results of observations that the children show poor abilities when playing football, when playing children do not show boredom or laziness, the children look happy when playing football.

The results of data collection obtained at TK Negeri Pembina Sibolangit showed that 7 of the 10 children observed were able to carry out activities well, namely, Evan, Rano, Annisa, Feby, Putri, Yepa, Lora. These children are able to carry out ball playing activities based on strength indicators in the descriptors of kicking the ball and passing the ball. And 3 children are not yet capable as described above.

Dribbling and Running Agility

In terms of agility indicators, which are viewed from the ability to dribble and run at TK Negeri Pembina Sibolangit, the results obtained from these observations show that 4 out of 10 children are still in the developing category, the data for these children are Putera, Afifah, Desman and Feby who are not yet able to carry out their activities. the activity of playing football. In

the description of dribbling and running, it can be seen that the child's ability to not yet be able to dribble the ball is also visible that the child almost fell and the ball slipped from the child's feet. When teachers and researchers ask children to repeat dribbling and running activities, the results or data that appear are still the same, the children's abilities in dribbling and running are still at the stage of starting to develop.

The results obtained from data collection were for 6 out of 10 children who were able to carry out dribbling and running activities, namely, Rano, Putri, Yepa, Lora, Evan, and Annisa. Children who show that they can move their feet very agilely and it seems that they are very enthusiastic and enjoy the pattern of playing football. These results found that out of 10 children, 6 of them were able to carry out the activities well, these 10 children carried out the activities very enthusiastically according to the directions of the teacher and researchers.

Ability to Balance Standing on One Leg and Holding the Ball

From the balance indicator with the descriptor standing on one leg and holding the ball passed by his playing partner. Data obtained from observations found that 7 out of 10 children, namely Lora, Evan, Annisa, Putri, Rano, Febi, and Yefa, had developed well and according to expectations for their gross motor skills on balance indicators. This can be seen from the fact that the children are able to stand on one foot and the child is also able to support his body on one leg when receiving a ball pass from his playmate. At the same time, the children were also seen kicking back the ball passed by their friends. They looked very enthusiastic about playing football.

In contrast to Afifah, Desman, and Putera, they still have difficulty maintaining their bodies, sometimes they lower their legs when carrying out the activities they are carrying out. They also cannot receive the ball passed by their friends, so in this activity the three children are still not developing as expected.

DISCUSSION

The Power of Kicking and Passing the Ball

The first indicator of children's gross motor skills at TK Negeri Pembina Sibolangit is strength. Where the child's gross motor skills in carrying out rough movements such as moving the body, jumping, sliding, going up and down stairs and kicking really require quite a lot of strength and use gross muscles. Mahatir and Gusril (2004) explain that strength is the skill or ability of muscles to generate force within a certain time. Early childhood must have muscle strength, because if a child does not have muscle strength the child will not be able to do physical play activities such as running, jumping and throwing. In the indicators and descriptors that have been implemented, there are 3 (30%) children who have difficulty in carrying out activities of kicking in a predetermined direction and passing the ball and 7 (70%) children are able to carry out these activities.

From the data presented above, it can be explained that the gross motor skills of children aged 5-6 years at TK Negeri Pembina Sibolangit have not fully developed according to expectations. There are still some children who have difficulty carrying out this activity, of the 10 children who were observed, only 7 children were able to carry out this activity. This can be seen because the child can kick well and pass well without making fatal mistakes, and has good coordination. from the feet of children doing these activities.

Herding and Running Agility

The second indicator of the gross motor skills of children aged 5-6 years from soccer playing activities is agility. Agility is a person's ability to change positions quickly and involve all components of the body. Agility also requires speed for changes in body position such as running back and forth and playing ball. Mahatir and Gusril (2004) stated that agility is a person's ability to change direction and body position quickly and within a certain time from one point to another.

The results of observations when carrying out observations showed that the gross motor skills of children aged 5-6 years for agility indicators were not completely evenly distributed, this is proven by the results of observations that have been made, it still shows that 4 out of 10 (40%) children are not yet able to carry out activities with these descriptors. What the researchers found was different from what should be expected, with children aged 5-6 years being able to run, stop and play ball. Where in the theory of Sujiono, et al (2010) related to gross motor skills, children aged 5-6 years are at least able to run, turn and stop effectively in a game. And according to Sumantri (2005), the development of children aged 5-6 years is at least able to jump, kick, bounce the ball, and have good agility.

Balance Standing on One Leg and Holding the Ball

The third indicator of the gross motor skills of children aged 5-6 years through the activity of playing football is balance with the descriptor standing on one leg and holding the ball passed by their playmate. Balance is a gross motor skill that requires gross muscles to coordinate to stabilize the body. According to Susanto (2012), explains that gross motor skills are movement patterns that involve the body and energy to use gross muscles and provide coordination in maintaining body stability or balance.

From the results of observations carried out by researchers at TK Negeri Pembina Sibolangit, it was found that 10 children, 8 (80%) of whom had good gross motor skills in terms of balance indicators. Where it is proven that they carry out balance gross motor activities well and easily, children are able to stand on one leg and children can hold the ball with one leg and can do it easily and stably. The child's ability to maintain his body on one leg means his coordination is highly developed and the child is at the level of development attainment that meets expectations. As stated by

Bredenkamp and Copple (Sujiono, 2015), children aged 5-6 years can already carry out activities such as standing on one leg for 5 seconds or more, mastering balance skills, standing on blocks. Children are also able to go down stairs with alternating feet, and can estimate where their feet stand well and precisely.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

Based on the various descriptions that researchers have put forward above regarding the gross motor skills of children aged 5-6 years through playing football at TK Negeri Pembina Sibolangit, Deli Serdang District, it can be concluded as follows:

- a. 70% of children's gross motor skills in the strength aspect have developed as expected and 30% have not developed as expected.
- b. 60% of children's gross motor skills in the agility aspect have developed as expected and 40% have not developed as expected.
- c. 80% of children's gross motor skills in the balance aspect have developed according to expectations and 20% have not developed as expected.

The results of each indicator found that gross motor skills developed as expected. Judging from the strength indicators, there were 7 children who were able to do well. In the agility indicator, 6 out of 10 children are able to carry out activities well. In the last indicator, namely the balance of 8 children who can carry out activities well and correctly. The game of football can also make every child happy, where children can play with their friends, run after the ball, kick the ball, catch the ball and throw the ball. This play pattern can influence the child's gross motor movement abilities.

Recommendations

The suggestions that researchers can give are:

- a. For Teachers

It is hoped that the gross motor skills of children aged 5-6, especially at TK Negeri Pembina Sibolangit, can be well stimulated in accordance with their age development and maturity. Teachers here can participate more in developing the gross motor skills of young children.

- b. For Parents

To focus more on stimulating the gross motor skills of children aged 5-6 years, guidance from parents is needed. Here the author also advises parents to pay attention to appropriate conditions and suitable games to further support children's motoric development so that it develops

according to the expectations and age maturity of early childhood.

- c. The results of research carried out by the author found that there are still some children who have not yet developed their gross motor skills, especially in terms of indicators of strength, agility and balance. Here the author also provides suggestions so that children's abilities can develop.

ADVANCED RESEARCH

For advanced research, we hope to be able to see or analyze data related to gross motor skills, especially for indicators of strength, agility and balance.

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